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Single and compound conditions

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Classical logic is based on exactly two truth values, either true or false. Meanwhile, for many, classical logic does represent our ultimate path to wisdom. In spite of everything, classical logic will certainly not stay our last and only possible view on natural phenomena. Especially an approach to objective reality from the point of view of many-valued logical is inclined to drop one fundamental assumption (true or not true) of classical logic and allow us more than only two truth values.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Some basic rules of classical logic have been used.

RESULTS:

We envisage a potential to approach to the issue of compound conditions especially from the point of view of pure classical logic.

CONCLUSION:

Conditions and compound conditions are one way to approach objective reality from the point of view of pure classical logic.

Keywords:

Conditions; Conditionals; Compound conditions; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

The identification of relationships between events is a very important aspect of any scientific inquiry and perhaps of everyday human activity too. However, such a human undertaking is conducted under certain conditions and is not easy. Various subjective or objective circumstances might have a positive or a negative influence on the outcome of any investigation. In other words, under the conditions of an epistemological fog, it is difficult to arrive at safe and reliable insights. And even if it appears that all things are going quite well, it is not automatically guaranteed that all objective factors have been properly considered. Systematic error or (selection, information, ..) bias might result from methods used by the investigator and can affect the validity of a study. In this understanding, it is highly attractive to rely on the methods of pure classical logic in order to arrive at reliable and long-lasting scientific insights. However, classical logic also has its limitations and the reduction of highly differentiated measurement values or information to merely true or false may also be insufficient occasionally. This is at least one of the reasons which leads to the necessity to develop a multi-valued, dialectical (see [Routley and Meyer, 1976](#)) or non-classical (see [van Benthem, 1979](#)) or para-consistent (see [Asenjo, 1966](#)) logic with complex truth values. However, any use of a non-classical (see [Birkhoff and Neumann, 1936](#)) or many-valued logic should work in a perfect and completely contradiction-free way with classical logic. This would appear to be possible, from a purely theoretical point of view, particularly if **the probability of a single event** is regarded as **the truth value** of dialectical, non-classical or multi-valued logic. Needless to say that the relation between classical and non-classical logic is comparable with the relation between the special and the general theory of relativity, the one passes without any contradiction into the other and vice versa.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Thought experiments

Like other experiments, scientific thought experiments can be criticised in different ways. However, thought experiments (see [Andreas, 2011](#); [Cargile et al., 1994](#); [McComb, 2013](#); [Rescher, 2005](#)) as one of the many methods of human investigation are used in many disciplines, including philosophy, mathematics, physics et cetera. Historically, view among the most brilliant practitioners of thought experimentation were Galileo, Newton, Leibniz, and other. And in our own time, it is fair to say that thought experiments were primarily an important method used in the philosophy of science. However, looking at the development of the thought experiments, we can't help but notice that the power of evidence featured by experimental results of a good thought experimental scenario need not to be any worse than that of a similar real world experimental scenario. Subjective and objective errors and other source of bias are a relatively simple, constantly recurring epistemological challenge and at the core of any real world experiment. Especially in the absence of the possibility of a high quality real world

experiment, thought experiments are opening up a strategic possibility for us to learn about objective reality by virtue of merely theoretical scenarios. Are we able to learn about objective reality (if we can at all), just by theoretical considerations? Scientific practice with room for thought experiments provokes in turn further inquiries into the relationship between theory and reality, especially with respect to phenomena that implicate both the natural sciences and theoretical sciences. In fact, may each reader at this point answer a fundamental question for themselves: can thought experiments really enable us at all to acquire new knowledge about nature without any empirical real world data? Of course, it is important not to downplay the significant differences between the real word experiments and thought experiments. However, an account of thought experiments seems more powerful if it can do justice to the fact that thought experiments can be a reliable and proven source of scientific knowledge. However one may like it, in principle, it seems difficult to erect a demarcation line between science and non-science along these lines of thought so perhaps it should be considered an open question. One by one and each issue at its own time.

2.1.2. Compound *conditio sine qua non* conditionals

A wide range of different approaches might assume that thought experiments are more or less only a meaningless and limiting case of ordinary experiments. A thought experiment might just happen on a theoretical level but is basically still an experiment with the intrinsic capacity to destroy prejudices about nature. At the centre of scientific thought experimenting are observations or data achieved by a concrete thought experiment which may be subject to a subsequent empirical analysis without discriminating a further ongoing investigation. Thus far, let A_t denote a (binomial, random, ...) yes–no condition with its own Boolean-valued outcome **either** true (+1) **or** false (= +0) at a certain, single (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45). Let $C_t...$ denote another (binomial, random, ..., or even a **compound**) yes–no condition with its own Boolean-valued outcome **either** true (+1) **or** false (= +0) at a certain, single (period of) time / **Bernoulli trial t** (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45).

Table 1. Compound conditio sine qua non conditionals

Bernoulli trial	A_i (1)	$C_1 \dots$ (2)	B_i (3)	$(A_i \wedge C_1 \dots)$ (4)	$(A_i \vee C_1 \dots)$ (5)	$(A_i \vee \overline{B_i})$ (6)	$(C_1 \dots \vee \overline{B_i})$ (7)	$(A_i \vee \overline{B_i}) \wedge (C_1 \dots \vee \overline{B_i})$ (9)	$((A_i \vee \overline{B_i}) \vee ((C_1 \dots) \vee \overline{B_i}))$ (10)	$((A_i \vee C_1 \dots) \vee \overline{B_i})$ (11)
t										
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
4	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
7	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 8$	4	4	4	2	6	6	5	5	7	7

Related to these data (see table 1) is the question whether we can recognise anything by this thought experiment.

2.1.3. Compound conditio sine qua non relationships

Let us consider the following data.

Table 2. Compound conditio sine qua non relationships

Bernoulli trial	A_t	B_t	C_t	$(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$	$(B_t \leftarrow C_t)$	$(A_t \leftarrow C_t)$	$((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t))$	$((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1
4	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
5	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
7	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
8	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 8$	4	4	4	6	6	6	4	8

Real-world example.

Let A_t denote a human cytomegalovirus (CMV) infection, let B_t denote a long-lasting smoking of cigarettes (smoking) by a human being, let C_t denote human lung cancer (LC). Human cytomegalovirus (CMV) or human herpesvirus-5 (HHV-5) is a member of the viral family known as herpesviruses. There is some, even if only preliminary, evidence, that the relationship

without CMV no smoking

is potentially given in reality ¹. Furthermore, there is additional evidence that the relationship

without smoking no LC

is valid ² too. Thus far what is or what could be the relationship between CMV and LC. As long as we may rely on the evidence of the above table (see table 2), the following conclusion

without CMV no LC

or

$$(((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)) = 1 \quad (1)$$

¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2019). Human cytomegalovirus is the cause of essential hypertension (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5549969>

²Barukčić, I. (2019). Smoking of tobacco is the cause of human lung cancer. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 9(1-s), 148-160. <https://doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v9i1-s.2273>

results with undeniable logical necessity ³. Should this presumed relationship between CMV and LC exist in reality too, traces of CMV should be found in every histological examination of lung cancer biopsies.

2.1.4. De Morgan's theorem

Augustus De Morgan (1806–1871) pointed to the possibility that an expression of conjunctions and disjunctions purely in terms of each other via negation is a valid rule of logical inference. Nonetheless, De Morgan's law (see [De Morgan, 1847](#), p. 118) was already known by William of Ockham in the 14th century (William of Ockham, *Summa Logicae*, part II, sections 32 and 33.). De Morgan wrote:

“The contrary of PQ is p,q; that of P,Q is pq ... is logically ‘not P and not Q’ or pq ”

(see [De Morgan, 1847](#), p. 118)

In simple words (see table 3), a negation of a disjunction is logically equivalent with the conjunction of the negations. In ordinary language, not (A or B) = (not A) and (not B).

Table 3. De Morgan's theorem

Bernoulli trial	A_t	\underline{A}_t	B_t	\underline{B}_t	$(A_t \vee B_t)$	$(\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$	$((\underline{A}_t) \wedge (\underline{B}_t))$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
2	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
3	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
4	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 4$	2	2	2	2	3	1	1

De Morgan's theorem simplifies different forms of reasoning and increases our ability to make

³Carpagnano GE, Lacedonia D, Natalicchio MI, Cotugno G, Zoppo L, Martinelli D, Antonetti R, Foschino-Barbaro MP. Viral colonization in exhaled breath condensate of lung cancer patients: Possible role of EBV and CMV. *Clin Respir J*. 2018 Feb;12(2):418-424. doi: 10.1111/crj.12531. Epub 2016 Jul 25. PMID: 27421948.

inferences more reliable. Furthermore (see table 4), a negation of a conjunction is logically equivalent with the disjunction of the negations. In ordinary language, not (A and B) = (not A) or (not B).

Table 4. De Morgan's theorem

Bernoulli trial	A_t	$\underline{A_t}$	B_t	$\underline{B_t}$	$(A_t \wedge B_t)$	$(\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{B_t})$	$((\underline{A_t}) \vee (\underline{B_t}))$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
2	1	0	0	1	0	1	1
3	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
4	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
...
$\Sigma = 4$	2	2	2	2	1	3	3

2.1.5. Compound conditio per quam conditionals

The following data achieved by a thought experiment (see table 5) serve to analyse and illustrate compound sufficient condition relationships.

Table 5. Compound conditio per quam conditionals

Bonoulli trial	A_1	$C_1 \dots$	B_t	$(A_1 \wedge C_1 \dots)$	$(A_1 \wedge C_1 \dots)$	$(A_1 \vee B_t)$	$(C_1 \dots \vee B_t)$	$((A_1 \wedge C_1 \dots) \vee B_t)$	$((A_1 \vee B_t) \vee (C_1 \dots \vee B_t))$	$((A_1 \vee B_t) \wedge (C_1 \dots \vee B_t))$	$((A_1 \vee C_1 \dots) \vee (B_t))$
t											
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
5	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
7	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
...
$\Sigma=8$	4	4	4	2	6	6	6	7	7	5	5

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*⁴ too.

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum ([Drude, 1894](#); [Tombe, 2015](#); [Weber and Kohlrausch, 1857, 1856](#)), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number ([Bombelli, 1579](#)). The number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) - (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv 0 \times 1 \quad (2)$$

while ‘=’ or \equiv denotes the equals sign ([Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign ([Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and ‘-’ ([Pacioli, 1494](#); [Widmann, 1489](#)) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and ‘+’ denotes the plus ([Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) ([Cotes and Halley, 1714](#)) or Leonhard Euler’s (1707 – 1783) identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations ([Wilson, 2018](#)). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler’s identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is logically sound and correct while the same is not investigated in detail.

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). Again, let c denote the speed of light in vacuum ([Drude, 1894](#); [Tombe, 2015](#); [Weber and Kohlrausch, 1857, 1856](#)), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number ([Bombelli, 1579](#)). The number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \quad (3)$$

while again ‘=’ or \equiv may denote the equals sign ([Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign ([Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and ‘-’ ([Pacioli, 1494](#); [Widmann, 1489](#)) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and ‘+’ denotes the plus ([Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

⁴Strobino, Riccardo, “Ibn Sina’s Logic”, The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

2.2.3. The infinity

Definition 2.3 (The infinity). *Let $+\infty$ denote positive infinity. Let $-\infty$ denote negative infinity.*

John Wallis (1616-1703), an English clergyman and mathematician, contributed to the development of infinitesimal calculus. Wallis defined especially the notion of infinity.

... esto enim ∞ nota numeri infiniti ...
(see Wallis, 1655, p. 21)

Infinity may possess many properties, while only view of these properties are identified by science. However, according to third parties, Albert Einstein in particular has urged great caution in this matter.

**“Two things are infinite, the universe and human stupidity,
and I am not yet completely sure about the universe.”**
(Albert Einstein according to Perls, 1969, p. 52)

2.2.4. Basic rules for exponentiation

Definition 2.4 (View basic rules of exponentiation). *Let $n = 1 + 1 + \dots$ denote a positive integer and let x denote any real number, then x^n corresponds to repeated multiplication as*

$$x^n \equiv \underbrace{x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \dots}_{n\text{-times}} \equiv x^{1+1+1+1+\dots} \quad (4)$$

From this definition, some basic rules of exponentiation can be deduced. It is

$$x^a \times x^b \equiv x^{a+b} \quad (5)$$

or

$$(x \times y)^a \equiv x^a \times y^a \quad (6)$$

or

$$\left(\frac{x^a}{y^a}\right) = \left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^a \quad (7)$$

or

$$(x^a)^b = (x^{a \times b}) = (x^b)^a \quad (8)$$

et cetera.

2.2.5. Logical operations

George Boole (1815-1864), a largely self-taught English mathematician, philosopher, and logician, published his monograph (see [Boole, 1854](#)) on algebraic logic in the year 1854. At least since George Boole, the basic values of classical bivalent logic and Boolean algebra are true, usually denoted by +1 and false, usually denoted by +0. In particular, after his very remarkable discovery

“ ... **aequationem ... causam et effectum ...** ”

([Leibniz, 1690](#), p. 201)

Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716) himself published in the year 1703 already the first self-consistent binary (see [Leibniz, 1703](#)) number system representing all numeric values while using typically +0 (zero) and +1 (one).

Definition 2.5 (Conjunction). *Conjunction is an logical operation and illustrated by table 6 in more detail. In particular, the equivalence of the logical operation conjunction (denoted by \wedge) and the arithmetic operation multiplication (denoted by \times) is eye catching.*

Table 6. Conjunction

Bernoulli trial	A_t	B_t	$(A_t \wedge B_t)$	$(A_t \times B_t)$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(3)
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0	0
3	0	1	0	0
4	0	0	0	0
...
$\Sigma = 4$	2	2	1	1

Definition 2.6 (Disjunction). *In classical bivalent logic, disjunction is a logical operation denoted by \vee .*

Table 7. Disjunction

Bernoulli trial	A_t	B_t	$(A_t \vee B_t)$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)
1	1	1	1
2	1	0	1
3	0	1	1
4	0	0	0
...
$\Sigma = 4$	2	2	3

Let $p(A_t)$ denote the probability of a single event A_t at the (period of) time/Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(B_t)$ denote the probability of a single event B_t at the (period of) time/Bernoulli trial t . Thus far, let $p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability of the events A_t and B_t (conjunction) at the (period of) time/Bernoulli trial t . Let $p(A_t \vee B_t)$ denote the disjunctive probability of the single events A_t or B_t at the (period of) time/Bernoulli trial t . In general, it is known that

$$p(A_t \vee B_t) + p(A_t \wedge B_t) = p(A_t) + p(B_t) \quad (9)$$

Definition 2.7 (Negation). *Negation, denoted by \neg in this context, is at least a relation by which every single entity, random variable et cetera at the (period of) time / Bernoulli trial t opposes itself in some way. This kind of self-relation, which everything has to itself, might be realised mathematically in various ways. From the point of view of Einstein's special theory of relativity, negation might adopt a different form in comparison classical logic or Boolean algebra. However, the simple nature of logical negation is the foundation any higher level forms of negation too. Many times, the concept of negation is often explained by a purely contradictory opposition between events. However, contradictory opposites can and should be distinguished from contrary opposites.*

Table 8. Negation

Bernoulli trial	A_t	$\neg A_t$	$((A_t) \wedge (\neg A_t))$	$((A_t) \vee (\neg A_t))$
t	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1	1	0	0	1
2	1	0	0	1
3	0	1	0	1
4	0	1	0	1
...
$\Sigma = 4$	2	2	0	4

Table 8 illustrates the fact, that there is no third between A_t and $\neg A_t$ (see table 8, column 4), a third is not given, *tertium non datur*. It is

$$p((A_t) \vee (\neg A_t)) + (p((A_t) \wedge (\neg A_t)) = 0) = p(A_t) + p(\neg A_t) = +1 \quad (10)$$

2.3. Axioms

Whether science needs new and obviously generally valid statements (axioms) which are able to assure the truth of theorems proved from them may remain an unanswered question. In order to be accepted, a new axiom candidate (see [Easwaran, 2008](#)) should be at least as simple as possible and logically consistent to enable advances in our knowledge of nature. The importance of axioms is particularly emphasized by Albert Einstein. “**Die wahrhaft großen Fortschritte der Naturerkenntnis sind auf einem der Induktion fast diametral entgegengesetzten Wege entstanden.**” (see [Einstein, 1919](#), p. 17). In general, *lex identitatis*, *lex contradictionis* and *lex negationis* have the potential to denote the most simple, the most general and the most far-reaching axioms of science, the foundation of our today’s and of our future scientific inquiry.

2.3.1. Principium identitatis (Axiom I)

Principium identitatis or **lex identitatis** or axiom I, is closely related to central problems of metaphysics, epistemology and of science as such. It turns out that it is more than rightful to assume that

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (11)$$

is true, otherwise there is every good reason to suppose that nothing can be discovered at all. Identity as the epitome of a self-identical or of self-reference is at the same time different from difference, identity is free from difference, identity is not difference, identity is at the same time the other of itself, identity is non-identity. Identity as simple equality with itself is determined by a non-being, by a non-being of its own other, by a non-being of difference, identity is different from difference. Identity is in its very own nature different and is in its own self the opposite of itself (symmetry). It is equally

$$-1 \equiv -1 \quad (12)$$

In general, +1 and -1 are distinguished, however these distinct are related to one and the same 1. Identity as a vanishing of otherness, therefore, is this distinguishedness in one relation. It is

$$0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv 0 \quad (13)$$

2.3.2. Principium contradictionis (Axiom II)

Principium contradictionis or **lex contradictionis**^{5, 6, 7} or axiom II, the other of *lex identitatis*, the negative of *lex identitatis*, the opposite of *lex identitatis*, a complementary of *lex identitatis*, can be expressed mathematically as

$$+0 \equiv 0 \times 1 \equiv +1 \quad (14)$$

In addition to the above, from the point of view of mathematics, axiom II (equation 14) is equally the most simple mathematical expression and formulation of a (logical) contradiction.

2.3.3. Principium negationis (Axiom III)

Lex negationis or axiom III, is often mismatched with simple opposition. However, from the point of view of philosophy and other sciences, identity, contradiction, negation and similar notions are equally mathematical descriptions of the most simple laws of objective reality. What sort of natural process is negation at the end? Mathematically, we define principium negationis or *lex negationis* or axiom III as

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times 0 \equiv \neg(0) \times 0 \equiv +1 \quad (15)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Ayer, 1952; Förster and Melamed, 2012; Hedwig, 1980; Heinemann, Fritz H., 1943; Horn, 1989; Koch, 1999; Kunen, 1987; Newstadt, 2015; Royce, 1917; Speranza and Horn, 2010; Wedin, 1990). In this context, there is some evidence that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 \equiv \neg(1) \times 1 = 0 \quad (16)$$

⁵Horn, Laurence R., "Contradiction", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Winter 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2018/entries/contradiction/>.

⁶Barukčić I. Aristotle's law of contradiction and Einstein's special theory of relativity. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics (JDDT)*. 15Mar.2019;9(2):125-43. <https://jddtonline.info/index.php/jddt/article/view/2389>

⁷Barukčić, Ilija. (2020, December 28). The contradiction is existing objectively and real (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396106>

Logically, it follows that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \equiv 0 \quad (17)$$

3. Results

In the following, let A_t denote an event, a condition et cetera, let B_t denote another event, an outcome, a conditioned et cetera, let $C_t \cdots$ a third condition or a numerous number of other conditions. Let t denote a certain (period of) time t / Bernoulli trial t . The repeated, (in-)finitely many, equally likely Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are independent. Each Bernoulli trial with exactly two possible outcomes, **either** true **or** false, is equally identically distributed. Next we will go on to examine the relationship of multiple conditions or events and to highlight the consequences.

4. Compound conditio sine qua non conditionals

4.1. *Theorem.* $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) = +1$

Theorem 1 $((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t))$. *The conditio sine qua non (SINE) or the necessary condition relationship between the events A_t and B_t is determined by the relation*

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1 \quad (18)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment with several theoretical Bernoulli trials has been performed. In the event of a necessary condition relationship, event B_t did not occur in the absence of event A_t (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 5$, column = 6, see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 7$, column = 6). \square

Real-world example.

Let A_t denote gaseous oxygen, let B_t denote human life. Gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life. In other words, **without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen **no** human life.

4.2. *Theorem.* $(C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = +1$

Theorem 2 $((C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t))$. *The conditio sine qua non (SINE) or the necessary condition relationship between the events $C_t \cdots$ and B_t is determined by the relation*

$$(C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1 \quad (19)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment with several theoretical Bernoulli trials has been performed. In the event of a necessary condition relationship, event B_t did not occur in the absence of event/s $C_t \cdots$ (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 3$, column = 7, see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 7$, column = 7). \square

Real-world example.

Let $C_t \cdots$ denote liquid water and/or other events, let B_t denote human life. Liquid water is another necessary condition of human life. In other words and independent of gaseous oxygen, **without** sufficient amounts of liquid water **no** human life.

4.3. *Theorem.* $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \neq (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t)$

Theorem 3 $((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \neq (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t))$. *In general, it is*

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \neq (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) \quad (20)$$

Proof by thought experiment. Again, a thought experiment with several theoretical Bernoulli trials has been performed. The necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) relationship $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 3$, column = 6) differs from the necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) relationship $(C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t)$ (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 3$, column = 7). Furthermore, in the event of a necessary condition relationship $(C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t)$ (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 5$, column = 7) the necessary condition relationship $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ is not given (see table 1, Bernoulli trial $t = 5$, column = 6).

□

Real-world example.

Let $C_t \cdots$ denote liquid water and/or other events, let A_t denote gaseous oxygen. Both events may be necessary condition of the event A_t . Besides of the fact that both are necessary conditions, both are different too and not the same.

4.4. *Theorem.* $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B}_t) = +1$

A_t is a necessary condition of B_t thus that $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1$ is given for sure. Let $C_t \cdots$ at the same (period of) time t / Bernoulli trial t be a necessary condition of B_t for sure too thus that $(C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1$.

Theorem 4 $((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B}_t))$. *In general, it is*

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B}_t) \quad (21)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The equivalence

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B}_t) \quad (22)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 8 and column = 9).

□

Real-world example.

Let $C_t \dots$ denote liquid water and/or other events, let A_t denote gaseous oxygen. Both events may be necessary condition of the event/outcome et cetera B_t . Besides of the fact that both are necessary conditions, both are different too and not the same. In general, it is true that **without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen **no** human life. Furthermore, **without** sufficient amounts of liquid water **no** human life too. These relationships are equivalent with the mathematical formulation **without** ((sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen) **and** (sufficient amounts of liquid water)) **no** human life (see theorem 4, equation 21).

At this point, we would like to illustrate the importance of theorem 4 in more detail, especially for medicine. Each person differs from other people and no two people are alike in the end. With this in mind, an ordinary person may suffer the temptation and claim something similar to the following. A mRNA Covid 19 vaccination (A_t) and the simultaneous presence of individual factors ($C_t \dots$) is the cause of myocarditis⁸ i suffer from. In other words, the hypothesis: **without** ((mRNA Covid 19 vaccination) and (other individual factors ($C_t \dots$))) **no** myocarditis is claimed to be valid. Whether such a hypothesis makes any sense or not, remains to be seen. Nonetheless, such a hypothesis can be tested. If the hypothesis before should be true, then according to theorem 4 it necessary to detect the relationship **without** (mRNA Covid 19 vaccination) **no** myocarditis in the sample or within the population. However, such a hypothesis is already historically wrong, because myocarditis occurred long before the existence of mRNA vaccination. In other words, historically, myocarditis occurred although mRNA vaccination did not exist or an mRNA vaccination has not been and is not a necessary condition of myocarditis. To bring it to the point, the hypothesis **without** (mRNA Covid 19 vaccination) **no** myocarditis is wrong. A straightforward logical consequence of theorem 4 is, that it is without any sense to search for additional individual factors like $C_t \dots$ which in combination with an mRNA vaccine might cause myocarditis⁹.

4.5. *Theorem.* $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \vee (C_t \dots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \vee C_t \dots) \vee \underline{B}_t) = +1$

Let A_t denote a necessary condition of B_t thus that $(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1$ is given for sure. Let $C_t \dots$ at the same (period of) time t / Bernoulli trial t be a necessary condition of B_t for sure too thus that $(C_t \dots \vee \underline{B}_t) = 1$.

Theorem 5 $((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \vee (C_t \dots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \vee C_t \dots) \vee \underline{B}_t))$. *In general, it is*

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \vee (C_t \dots \vee \underline{B}_t) = ((A_t \vee C_t \dots) \vee \underline{B}_t) \quad (23)$$

⁸Schwab C, Domke LM, Hartmann L, Stenzinger A, Longerich T, Schirmacher P. Autopsy-based histopathological characterization of myocarditis after anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccination. Clin Res Cardiol. 2022 Nov 27:1–10. doi: 10.1007/s00392-022-02129-5. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 36436002; PMCID: PMC9702955.

⁹Barukčić, Ilija. mRNA Covid - 19 vaccination and myocarditis: no causal relationship. Causation. 2022;18(8):29-45. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7454317

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The equivalence

$$(A_t \vee \underline{B_t}) \vee (C_t \cdots \vee \underline{B_t}) = ((A_t \vee C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \quad (24)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 10 and column = 11) for sure.

□

4.6. *Theorem.* $((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \neq ((A_t \vee C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t})$

Theorem 6 $((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \neq ((A_t \vee C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t})$. *In general, it is*

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \neq ((A_t \vee C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \quad (25)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The non-equivalence

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \neq ((A_t \vee C_t \cdots) \vee \underline{B_t}) \quad (26)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 8 and column = 11) for sure.

□

4.7. *Theorem.* $(((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)) = +1$

Theorem 7 $((((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)) = +1$). *In general, it is*

$$(((A_t \leftarrow B_t) \wedge (B_t \leftarrow C_t)) \rightarrow (A_t \leftarrow C_t)) = +1 \quad (27)$$

Proof by direct proof. Notice the relationship of the expressions in column (4), (5), (6) and column (7) (see table 2). The proof *if* $((A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ and $(B_t \leftarrow C_t))$ *then* $(A_t \leftarrow C_t)$ (see table 2, column (8)) provided is logically consistent and imperative .

□

5. Compound conditio per quam conditionals

Despite the overwhelming reasoning of Philo of Megara (see [Astorga, 2015](#); [Mates, 1949](#)), who proposed that the conditional ‘if A_t then B_t ’ (see [Frege, 1879](#); [Russell and Whitehead, 1910](#)) is true exactly when it is not the case that A_t is true and B_t is false, there is surprisingly little agreement about the right logic of multiple or compound conditionals. We go on to examine a sufficient condition and two or more sufficient conditionals at one and the same Bernoulli trial t .

5.1. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) = +1$

Theorem 8 ($(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) = +1$). *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (28)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 5) are obtained and documented. The sufficient condition relationship (IMP) is given as

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (29)$$

(see table 1, column = 7).

□

5.2. *Theorem.* $(\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) = +1$

Theorem 9 ($(\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) = +1$). *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (30)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The equivalence

$$(\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (31)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 8).

□

5.3. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \neq (\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t)$

Theorem 10 ($(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \neq (\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t)$). *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \neq (\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) \quad (32)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The non-equivalence

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \neq (\underline{C_t \cdots} \vee B_t) \quad (33)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 7 and column = 8).

□

5.4. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) \neq ((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t)$

Theorem 11 $((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) \neq ((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = +1)$. *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) \neq ((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) \quad (34)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The non-equivalence

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) \neq ((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) \quad (35)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 9 and column = 11).

□

5.5. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = +1$

Theorem 12 $((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = +1)$. *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (36)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The equivalence

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{C_t \dots} \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (37)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 11 and column = 12).

□

5.6. *Theorem.* $((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \vee ((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t)) = +1$

Theorem 13 $((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \vee ((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t)) = +1)$. *In general, it is*

$$((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \vee ((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t)) = +1 \quad (38)$$

Proof by thought experiment. A thought experiment is performed and repeated once and again. Data (see table 1) are obtained and documented. The equivalence

$$((\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t) = ((\underline{A_t} \vee B_t) \vee ((\underline{C_t \dots}) \vee B_t)) = +1 \quad (39)$$

is proofed (see table 1, column = 9 and column = 10).

□

Real-world example.

In order to understand the meaning of the previous theorem 13, let us consider the following. Let A_t denote the natural process of raining at a certain place at the Bernoulli trial t . Let $C_t \dots$ denote the natural process of pouring a small amount of water on the street by an individual et cetera at the same place at the Bernoulli trial t . Let B_t indicate the state of the street, which is **either** wet **or** not wet. In general, the following relationship is true: **if** it is raining at a certain place at the Bernoulli trial t , **then** the street is wet at this place at the same Bernoulli trial t . In other words, it is (A:)

$$((\textit{raining})_t \vee (\textit{street is wet})_t) = +1 \quad (40)$$

Furthermore, it is true that **if** an individual is pouring a small amount of water on the street at a certain place at the Bernoulli trial t , **then** the street is wet at the same place at the same Bernoulli trial t . In general, it is (B:)

$$((\textit{pouring a small amount of water on the street})_t \vee (\textit{street is wet})_t) = +1 \quad (41)$$

Under conditions where the relationships $((\textit{raining})_t \vee (\textit{street is wet})_t) = +1$ and $((\textit{pouring a small amount of water on the street})_t \vee (\textit{street is wet})_t) = +1$ are equally true it follows with indispensable pure logical consequence that

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = ((A_t \vee B_t) \vee (C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (42)$$

Now, what is the most practical added value which theorem 13 is providing to us and which conclusions can we draw from it?

A case from real life could be helpful. In the vast majority of events, vaccinations such as mRNA-Covid 19 vaccinations (A_t) are strongly recommended as effective and safe at preventing death or serious illness from Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) or Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) disease. Occasionally, however, events or diseases occur in a close temporal interval with respect to such a mRNA vaccination. A person who suffers from an outcome B_t , which is at the same time additionally characterised by an event ($C_t \dots$), could justifiably suspect that a mRNA vaccination (A_t) administered in connection with an event ($C_t \dots$) has been a sufficient condition of his outcome (B_t). In other words, from the point of view of classical logic, it is alleged that

$$((A_t \wedge C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (43)$$

Is there any objective evidence that the person before is a victim of vaccination damage? Such a question certainly occupies many which have to deal with serious side effects associated with vaccines. We think an appropriate way of addressing such an issue is the application of theorem 13. According to theorem 13, it is necessary to provide evidence proving that

$$((A_t) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (44)$$

and that

$$((C_t \dots) \vee B_t) = +1 \quad (45)$$

In other words, it is necessary to proof for sure that the sufficient condition **if** ((mRNA vaccination)_t) **then** (myocarditis)_t is true. Furthermore, independently of the necessity to establish this relationship, it is necessary to proof that the sufficient condition **if** (C_t ···) **then** (myocarditis)_t is also true. Only under these circumstances it would be justified to conclude that the compound sufficient condition **if** ((mRNA vaccination) and (C_t ···)) **then** (myocarditis)_t is also true. Meanwhile, millions of people have been vaccinated by a mRNA COVID-19 vaccine without suffering from myocarditis. It is important to underline that a mRNA COVID-19 vaccine is not a sufficient condition of myocarditis. Therefore, to put it concisely, according to theorem 13, it is not ¹⁰ possible ¹¹ that ((mRNA vaccination) and (C_t ···)) is a sufficient condition of (myocarditis)_t. In other words, the relationship **if** ((mRNA vaccination) and (C_t ···)) **then** (myocarditis)_t is false. Despite all conceivable adversities, a sufficient condition relationship is not identical with causality. However, the same study or different studies should be able to prove a necessary condition relationship or a sufficient condition relationship between events investigated or best both, a necessary and sufficient condition relationship in order to enable us to deal with the question of a possible causal relationship between events investigated.

5.7. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{B_t}) = ((\underline{A_t}) \wedge (\underline{B_t}))$

Theorem 14 (Not(A or B) = Not(A) and Not(B)). *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \vee \underline{B_t}) = ((\underline{A_t}) \wedge (\underline{B_t})) \quad (46)$$

Proof by direct proof. Notice the equivalency of the expressions in column (6) and column (7) of table 3. The proof provided is logically consistent and imperative (see table 3, column (6) and column (7)).

□

5.8. *Theorem.* $(\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{B_t}) = ((\underline{A_t}) \vee (\underline{B_t}))$

Theorem 15 (Not(A and B) = Not(A) or Not(B)). *In general, it is*

$$(\underline{A_t} \wedge \underline{B_t}) = ((\underline{A_t}) \vee (\underline{B_t})) \quad (47)$$

Proof by direct proof. Notice the equivalency of the expressions in column (6) and column (7) of table 4. The proof provided is logically consistent and imperative (see table 4, column (6) and column (7)).

□

¹⁰Barukčić, Ilija. mRNA Covid - 19 vaccination and myocarditis: no causal relationship. *Causation* 2022;18:29–45. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7454317>.

¹¹Schwab C, Domke LM, Hartmann L, Stenzinger A, Longerich T, Schirmacher P. Autopsy-based histopathological characterization of myocarditis after anti-SARS-CoV-2-vaccination. *Clin Res Cardiol.* 2022 Nov 27:1–10. doi: 10.1007/s00392-022-02129-5. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 36436002; PMCID: PMC9702955.

6. Discussion

Historically, any concept of scientific evidence is and has been central to both philosophy and (natural) science as such. No wonder that there is an increasing interest in innovative methods of scientific investigation and inference in order to explore and provide deeper insights into real-world problems. In this context, the development and study of classical logic based scientific methods is an attempt to provide scientist and other people with rigorous, methodologically sound means of investigation. And much more than this. Classical logic based approaches to data collection and analysis are able to provide us with additional insights beyond that obtained via conventional (statistical) methods. Needless to say and as not to prejudice any further investigations on this matter, the proofs provided in this publication even if formally correct and robust are very simple too. So we might ask: can we rely heavily on the proofs provided in this publication to justify even far reaching claims. Put differently, and more boldly, to what extent can sciences rely on the methods outlined in this paper in order to investigate the mind-independent existence of relationships of objective reality. Although highly abstract proofs might in some sense provide evidence which makes a theory more likely to be true, it seems reasonable, moreover, to say that even highly abstract, (mathematically) logic based proofs of the theorems published in this paper will only confirm the logical truth of the theorems developed in this paper in its purest form. However, the epistemological weight of such proofs do not have to be better than the power of the simplest possible proofs presented at this occasion. On other, more widespread views, as in other areas of sciences, classical logic is as a method of scientific discovery too, while a lot depends upon the details.

7. Conclusion

Our non-ending desire to reveal even the deepest secrets of nature is satisfied by appropriate scientific methods too.

‘Methods based on classical logic can help us to recognise what might be true, what is not true but could have been and what should be done to discover the way things are.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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Associated Data

None.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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